

FUNDAMENTALS OF GENERAL THEORETICAL STUDY OF TERMS

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Abstract. The term and the problem of terminology are part of the general theory of linguistics. The concept of the term brings everything related to learning closer to linguistics not only to various areas of scientific knowledge, but also to various areas of production practice and professional work. in any case, here the development of the language, its lexical system is clearly connected with the material and spiritual history of the nation.

Key words: Terms, terminology, concept, linguistics, technology, lexicon.

Абстракт. Термин и проблема терминологии являются частью общей теории языкознания. Понятие термина сближает все, что связано с обучением с лингвистикой, не только с различными областями научного знания, но и с различными областями производственной практики и профессиональной деятельности. во всяком случае здесь развитие языка, его лексического строя явно связано с материальной и духовной историей нации.

Ключевые слова: Термины, терминология, концепт, языкознание, технология, лексика.

INTRODUCTION As a result of the rapid growth of modern technical development, terminology is also being formed in parallel. That's why it is necessary to know the linguistic basis of the terms in order to understand the existing essence of the terms and terms related to the field, to understand the meaning expressed by it.

The term is derived from the Greek word, which means check, boundary. It is a word specific to science, technology, agriculture, art and culture. Terminology means the study of terms and a set of terms. In place of the word term, there are cases of using term, istilah words as well. But this is not true. The term represents a narrow understanding of the word term. The word istilah is Arabic. It is not understood by the people and it has not become the norm.

MAIN PART Terminology issues have always been one of the topical issues of linguistics. Because determining the place and function of the terms in the dictionary layers of the fields, allows to understand the meaning of the concept correctly. In all the works devoted to terminology, the units that represent specific concepts of one or another field, have a definition and mainly perform a nominative function are considered to be terms. A. Reformatsky defines the term and concludes that "... terms are special words". [Reformatsky. A; 2001]. [A.V. Kalinin; 2002] calls the words used in certain disciplines and professions "special lexicon" and divides it into two groups:

1. The special lexicon includes, first of all, terms.
2. In addition to terms, the special lexicon also includes professionalisms.

He continued his opinion and said, "The difference between the term and professionalism is that the term is the expression and name of a concept that is official, accepted and legislated in a particular field of science, industry, agriculture, technology, and professionalism is a Profession, specialty is a semi-official word that is often used in everyday language and does not have a strict, scientific description of the concept. R. Doniyorov objects to this opinion and says, "We will not make a mistake if we say that such a firm claim is, in fact, a continuation of the views of some "scientists" who consider language to be class-based." [Doniyorov; 2011]] H. Jamolkhanov defines the term as follows:

"Terms are nominative units representing specialized concepts related to science and technology, literature, art and other fields, whose application is limited

to a specific field: glucose, rectangle, square (in geometry); have, participle (in linguistics); rhyme, balance, weight (in literary studies)" etc. [Jamalkhanov; 2013]

The expression plan of the terms is equivalent to a word (cell, tissue) or a fixed combination (arrow root, ankle root). In fact, it would be appropriate if experts in the field and terminological scientists work together to ensure that the terms being changed or replaced are simple, concise, and most importantly, understandable to the public. Preservation of the linguistic resources of the mother tongue, which embodies the centuries-old experience of every people, their scientific analysis, and passing them on to the next generations is one of the important tasks facing modern science, in particular, linguistics and translation studies. From this point of view, as the first president of Uzbekistan, I. A. Karimov, said, "the Uzbek language, which is a means of expressing the national culture and identity of the people," contains words and phrases, terms and lexical learning and carrying out scientific analysis as a linguistic heritage is one of the most urgent issues today.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION The terminological lexicon, which A. A. Potebnya called "next meaning" and indicated that "it does not belong to the object of study of linguistics, it is studied by other disciplines", will not be recognized in linguistics as a separate nominative unit, term for a long time. As the science of linguistics developed and expanded its scope of research, the study of terms became one of its most important and structural senses. In the present period, the study of terms has formed a separate field of linguistics - terminology[Potebnya;].

It is also worth noting that it is necessary to pay special attention to the description of the text of the terminology of the fields in accordance with the requirements of the literary orthographic, lexical and stylistic criteria. Because the texts presented to the public should be concise, simple and understandable. In this regard, one of the areas that we encounter more often is the language of various guidelines and recommendations in socio-political documents and other terminological layers. It is true that it is difficult to understand the expressions

described in some texts at the first reading. You will hardly understand the information you need by reading it over and over again.

In relation to terms, it is very important to act in accordance with the laws of development of the language, specific objective requirements, criteria, scientific measurement and principles of standardizing its lexical system in updating, changing and improving the terminological system.

Ulug Tursunov was one of the first to try to clarify the issues of the terminology of the Uzbek language and wrote works dedicated to this issue: "Against the aspirations of the bourgeoisie in language-terminology", "Issues of Uzbek terminology", "Issues of terminology", "Principles of choosing words and terms in the Uzbek literary language". These works reflect on various views and concepts in the field of term generation, collection, arrangement, unification and publication. In addition, it is noted that the confusions that have occurred and are occurring in the field of terminology are beginning to be clearly visible. For example, one concept can be spelled and written in different ways; providing long explanations instead of clear and concise terms; less use of native language opportunities in term creation; It was shown that one of the sources of enrichment of Uzbek terminology is the fact of different approaches to the external factor. Mechanical engineering terms are distinguished from terms of other fields by the richness of special terms (and abbreviations), the traditionality of word usage, and the relatively greater use of some syntactic expressions. The presence of a large number of special terms in a text (especially a text related to technologies), especially those that have recently appeared (neologisms) and have not yet been recorded in dictionaries, has led to significant difficulties in practice. The abundance of such new terms in the field of mechanical engineering is explained by the fact that terms are a dynamic layer of the language vocabulary. The vocabulary of the language is continuously replenished, and this linguistic phenomenon is the naming and naming of new concepts and phenomena that have arisen as a result of the intensive development of science and technology in recent

years due to the development of science and technology, the increase of their position in society. new special terms account created for

The machine is made of the same material and cannot be separated into pieces the smallest part is called detail. (For example: nut, bolt, key, spring, etc.)

A part of the machine designed to perform a certain task and made up of several details is called a unit. (for example: reducer, coupling, bearing and etc.). So, the machine is made of nodes, and the nodes are made of details. There are many such details and components that are used in almost all types of cars. These include gears, shafts, couplings, etc. The structure of these details and nodes and their design methods are studied in the science of machine detailing.

Formation and practice of the terminological system is one of the important issues in linguistics. In modern linguistics, it is not only the study of existing terms and terms, but also the factors and conditions that cause the formation of new terms, its signs as a lexical unit, and its semantic significance. According to O.A. Kornilova, the scientific understanding of the world is expressed in the "language of science", more precisely, in the language of each science. The core of a certain scientific language is, without a doubt, the terms used in it, that is, the lexical-semantic units that express scientific concepts and categories. Therefore, it can be concluded that the scientific landscape of the world is strengthened in terms of science" [Kornilov;]

Although there is an interaction between terminology and generalizations, it is the specific terms that are most important in the history of technical progress.

Terms serve as a means of fixing knowledge and experiences in special fields. Therefore, it is only through the successful transfer of learned skills and experiences that the continued development of the field can be ensured.

The purpose of terminological works related to any field of science and technology is mutual understanding and cooperation of specialists of a specific field of science and related to it, dictionary, publishing works, reading and studying within this field is to ensure the quality of the teaching process. This, in

turn, requires that each term in the terminological system means a single clear concept and is created according to the laws of the Uzbek language. Most of the terms used in the textbooks and manuals, scientific and popular works, dictionaries in the field of mechanical engineering are formed based on the internal laws of the Uzbek language and clearly express the concepts, which is the basis of the teaching-learning process. It can be seen that it helps to meet the current requirements.

CONCLUSION The study of the original and translated works in the Uzbek language, bilingual and terminological dictionaries, textbooks created in the field of mechanical engineering showed that the Uzbek mechanical engineering field terminology, as in the terminological systems of other fields of science, has a number of shortcomings and flaws. From this point of view, there is a need to deal separately with the issues of regulating the field terms of the Uzbek language.

Terms related to technology, cotton farming, botany, linguistics, literature, mathematics, physics, music, medicine, chemistry, electrical engineering, types of folk arts and other fields have been studied in detail from a linguistic point of view, and specific recommendations have been developed for their arrangement. However, a comprehensive monograph on general theoretical issues of Uzbek terminology has not yet been created. The main reason for this is that, firstly, the formation, development and enrichment of the existing terminological systems in the Uzbek language are not at the same level, and secondly, the terminologies of some scientific fields have not been studied well.

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